

Strength Reductions Due to Interaction of Buckling Modes in Equal Lipped Angle Compression Members

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ABSTRACT

The possible failure modes of cold-formed steel (CFS) lipped angle (LA) compression members are yielding, local, flexural-torsional or flexural buckling, and any possible interaction between these buckling modes. In general, the strength estimated by current design guidelines are conservative for these members when flexural-torsional buckling (FTB) is the first global buckling mode as the post-buckling strength of this mode is not accounted for in the global buckling strength equations. The initial part of this paper reports the results of an experimental and numerical study of CFS-LA members undergoing independent FTB. The modifications are suggested to global buckling strength equations based on these results. Subsequently, the reduction in the ultimate strength from strength corresponding to independent buckling modes for LA members undergoing interaction between buckling modes such as local-flexural torsional, flexural-flexural torsional, local-flexural, and local-flexural torsional-flexural are studied systematically using finite element analysis results. A simple and more accurate interaction equation that accounts for above interactions between buckling modes in CFS-LA compression members is proposed.

Keywords: Cold-formed steel, Lipped angle, Flexural-torsional buckling, Local buckling, Buckling interaction.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cold-formed steel (CFS) equal leg lipped angle (LA) compression members may undergo local buckling, flexural-torsional buckling (FTB) and flexural buckling about minor axis, or interaction among these modes. The effective width method (EWM) (1 - 4) and direct strength method (DSM) (1, 2) can be used for evaluating the strength of these members as local-global (LG) interaction. These methods are generally conservative for CFS-LAs when FTB is the first global buckling mode, since the post-buckling strength of this mode is not accounted for in the current global buckling strength equation, Eq. 1 (8 – 11).

$$\frac{P_{ug}}{P_y} = \begin{cases} 0.658\lambda_g^2 & \lambda_g \leq 1.5 \\ \frac{0.877}{\lambda_g^2} & \lambda_g > 1.5 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The initial part of this paper discusses the FTB behavior of CFS-LA compression members. In this study, 15 CFS-LA compression members having fixed end boundary conditions undergoing only FTB before failure were tested. The interactions of local and flexural buckling modes were eliminated by carefully choosing the geometric and material properties of the specimens. Further, a detailed parametric study was carried out using finite element analysis (FEA) which was initially validated using the experimental results. The modification to the global buckling strength equation to account for the post-buckling strength of the LA compression member in FTB mode is proposed based on test and FEA results.

The results of a detailed numerical investigation of different possible interactions of buckling modes such as local-flexural torsional (L-FT), flexural-flexural torsional (F-FT), local-flexural (L-F), and local-flexural torsional-flexural (L-FT-F) in CFS-LA compression members are presented subsequently in this paper. The reduction in the strength from strength corresponding to independent buckling modes due to interaction is demonstrated using FEA results. A simple and accurate interaction equation that accounts for interaction between all possible buckling modes in CFS-LA compression members is proposed in this study using experimental and FEA results.

2 EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The experiments in the present study are limited to independent FTB mode as there are no such experiments reported in literature. The specimens tested by Young (10) were prone to interactions from local and/or flexural modes.

A total of 15 specimens were press-braked from galvanized steel sheets of 2 and 3mm nominal thicknesses and having nominal yield strengths, f_y , of 250 and 300MPa. The material properties of the specimens were determined by testing the tensile coupon as per ASTM (3). The dimensions and material properties were chosen to ensure that these specimens are not influenced by local or minor axis buckling modes. The ratio of elastic local and minor axis buckling loads to FTB load (P_{cr1}/P_{crft} and P_{crf-v}/P_{crft} , respectively) of the test specimens are much higher than 1.0 which ensures independent FTB mode. A milled steel plate of thickness 8mm was welded at each end of the test specimen. The specimen ends were also milled before welding for precise bearing contact with the endplates. The 500kN actuator (MTS model 322.41) was used to apply the compression using displacement control at a rate of 0.2mm/min. Four 5mm-strain gauges (SG) were fixed on both sides of the flanges in the longitudinal direction at mid-length of the specimen. Initially, a displacement up to 0.1mm was applied and unloaded. The test was continued only if the readings of SG-1, 2, 3, and 4 were nearly equal which indicated uniform compression over the cross-section in the initial stage of loading. Two linear variable displacement transducers (LVDT) were placed on both sides of the top end plate to measure the axial deformation and one LVDT on the flange at mid-height for measuring the lateral deformation of the specimens.

Fig 1: Test and FEA results: (a) longitudinal strain plot of LA6; (b) axial stress vs. axial displacement plots of LA6 and LA10

All specimens tested in this study failed due to FTB without any sign of other modes or their interaction. The axial strains from SG1 to 4 shown in *Fig. 1a* for LA6 150x10x3x1800 indicates uniform deformation of the test specimen in the initial phase of loading. The elastic global buckling stress, $f_{cr-test}$ determined using the Southwell plot (SWP) from the lateral deformation is also marked in *Fig. 1a* for comparison. The detailed discussion of SWP was presented in Kumar and Kalyanaraman (6). The average axial stress versus axial deformation curves of two specimens (LA6 150x10x3x1800 and LA10 100x6x2x1000) are given in *Fig. 1b*.

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODELING AND VALIDATION

The additional data for the ultimate strength, P_u for fixed-ended CFS-LA compression members were generated by analyzing nonlinear finite element (FE) models using ABAQUS, finite element package. Four noded shell elements with reduced integration (S4R elements) were used to model geometry along the mid-thickness of the plate elements of the cross-section. The mesh size of around 6 x 6mm based on mesh convergence studies with at least 3 elements along lip depth was used. The corners were modeled as sharp corners (8) and residual stresses were ignored in the modeling due to negligible influence. All nodes at each end of the FE model was connected along the edge using three-dimensional beam elements (B33) with high in plane flexural stiffness of the shell elements to avoid stress concentration due to concentrated load and/or support reaction. The same beam elements were used to connect these nodes to the centroid (CG) of the cross-section where the load and boundary conditions were applied. All translations and rotations were restrained at the end nodes at centroid except the longitudinal translation at one end where the displacement was applied.

All 15 specimens tested in this study that failed due to independent FTB and 25 specimens tested by Young (10) were modelled for extending the study to buckling mode interactions in LAs. Extensive parametric study is conducted using the validated finite element model. The average axial compressive stress (=load/gross-area) versus axial displacement of two specimens LA6 and LA10 from test and FEA are presented in *Fig. 1b*. The mean and standard deviation of the ratio of ultimate strengths from tests conducted as part of this study and those by Young (10) to FEA (P_{u-test}/P_{u-FEA}) are 0.99 and 0.07, respectively which indicates the accuracy of FEA results.

4 FLEXURAL TORSIONAL BUCKLING

Based on the validated finite element model initially the independent FTB behavior of CFS-LA compression members are studied. A total of 200 FE models with b (50-150mm), d/b (0.04-0.25), L (500-3000mm), L/b (5-20), λ_{ft} (0.58-3.11), and f_y (200-650 MPa) were analysed to study the independent FTB behaviour of CFS-LA compression members. The geometry and material properties of the FE model were carefully chosen such that P_{crft} and P_{u-FEA} are much smaller than P_{crf-v} and P_{crl} ($3.3 \leq P_{crf-v}/P_{crft} \leq 109.5$, $2.7 \leq P_{crl}/P_{crft} \leq 11.0$ and $3.3 \leq P_{crf-v}/P_{u-FEA} \leq 85.2$, $1.2 \leq P_{crl}/P_{u-FEA} \leq 25.9$). Hence, the interaction of FTB with both local and flexural buckling modes was considered to be negligible.

$$\frac{P_{uft-young}}{P_y} = \begin{cases} 0.5\lambda_{ft}^2 & \lambda_{ft} \leq 1.4 \\ \frac{0.5}{\lambda_{ft}^2} & \lambda_{ft} > 1.4 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{P_{uft-shifferaw}}{P_y} = \begin{cases} 0.735\lambda_{ft}^2 & \lambda_{ft} \leq 1.264 \\ \left(1 - \frac{0.25}{\lambda_{ft}^{1.2}}\right) \frac{1}{\lambda_{ft}^{1.2}} & \lambda_{ft} > 1.264 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{P_{uft-Proposed}}{P_y} = \begin{cases} 0.77\lambda_{ft}^2 & \lambda_{ft} \leq 1 \\ \left(1 - \frac{0.23}{\lambda_{ft}^{0.6}}\right) \frac{1}{\lambda_{ft}^{0.6}} & \lambda_{ft} > 1 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The results are compared to the current global buckling strength equation, Eq. 1 (1) and to modified equations proposed by Young (9) and Shifferaw and Schafer (8), Eqs. 2 and 3 respectively. Equation 4 is proposed based on the modified distortional buckling equation by Kumar and Kalyanaraman (6). The normalized ultimate strength, P_u/P_y and the ratio of ultimate strengths from test and FEA to that from theory (Eqs. 1,2,3,4), $P_{u-test,FEA}/P_{u-theory}$ against nondimensional FTB slenderness are plotted in Fig. 3.

Fig 3: Results of LAs under independent FTB

The observations are as follows:

1. The CFS-LA specimens show post-buckling strength in FTB mode for FTB slenderness greater than 1.50. Hence, the ultimate strength, P_u obtained from the global buckling strength equations (Eqs. 1, 2) are conservative. The mean (= 2.91, 5.03) and standard deviation (= 1.17, 2.15) of $P_{u-test,FEA}/P_{u-theory}$ indicate the poor performance of these equations.
2. The statistics (mean= 1.48, standard deviation = 0.28 of $P_{u-test,FEA}/P_{u-theory}$ has improved significantly while using Eq. 3 as it accounts for the post-buckling strength (Fig. 3).
3. The ultimate strength from proposed equation (Eq. 4) shows the best statistics (mean = 0.97, and standard deviation = 0.05 of $P_{u-test,FEA}/P_{u-theory}$ compared to all other methods (Eqs. 1, 2, 3).

5 INTERACTION OF BUCKLING MODES

Initially the independent local buckling behavior of LA compression members is explored. Based on the FEA results the modified local buckling strength equation by Kumar and Kalyanaraman (5) is found to give comparable predictions to the current EWM and DSM design procedures. The study is then extended to all the different cases of mode interactions namely L-FT, F-FT, L-F and L-FT-F interactions. The ratio of ultimate strength from FEA (P_{u-FEA}) to the minimum of theoretical strengths corresponding to independent buckling modes are the ordinates in Fig. 4. The maximum reduction in the strength below the values of strength under independent buckling mode is 45%, 57%, 33% and 51% for L-FT, F-FT, L-F and L-FT-F interactions, respectively as observed in Figs. 4a,b,c and d respectively.

6 PROPOSED INTERACTION EQUATION

The proposed interaction equation (PIE), Eq. 5 which is similar to the interaction equation proposed by Kumar and Kalyanaraman (7) for CFS lipped channels, estimates the strength of LA compression members using the independent local, flexural-torsional and flexural buckling strengths. Based on 1015 FEA and 40 test results it is observed that Eq. 5 has mean = 1.05, and standard deviation = 0.12 of $P_{u-test,FEA}/P_{u-theory}$ and is found to accurately represent all the independent buckling modes as well as the different cases of mode interactions. The current EWM and DSM design procedures are found to give mean=1.98, 2.05 and standard deviation = 1.05 and 1.50, respectively which indicates the poor performance of these methods.

$$\frac{P_{u-l,ft,f}}{P_y} = 0.08 + \left(\frac{P_{u-ft}}{P_y} \times \frac{P_{u-l}}{P_y} \times \frac{P_{u-f-v}}{P_y} \right) \leq \text{Minimum of} \left(\frac{P_{u-ft}}{P_y}, \frac{P_{u-l}}{P_y}, \frac{P_{u-f-v}}{P_y} \right) \quad (5)$$

Fig 4: Strength reduction due to buckling mode interactions in LAs: (a) L-FT; (b) F-FT; (c) L-F; (d) L-FT-F interactions

7 CONCLUSIONS

Initially, the results of experimental tests of 15 fixed-ended CFSLA compression members that failed after only FTB were reported. Subsequently, FE models were prepared and validated using the test results generated in this study as well as the test results reported by Young (10). Using validated FE models, the behavior of CFSLA compression members failing due to an independent buckling mode (flexural-torsional or local) and interaction of buckling modes (L-FT, F-FT, L-F, and L-FT-F) was studied systematically. The conclusions from this study are as follows:

1. The comparison with 15 experimental and 200 FEA results of specimens that failed due to only FTB showed the presence of post-buckling capacity which is not accounted for in current design procedures. The proposed equation (Eq. 4) accounts for the post-buckling strength in FTB using MDSM-DB equation Kumar and Kalyanaraman (6) for $\lambda_{ft} > 1.0$ and is found to be more accurate than Eqs. 1, 2 and 3.
2. The interaction between buckling modes leads to the reduction in the ultimate strength from strength corresponding to independent buckling modes is demonstrated using FEA results. In general, EWM and DSM estimate the strength of CFS-LAs conservatively compared to test or FEA results. The proposed interaction equation (PIE) which is similar to the interaction equation proposed by Kumar and Kalyanaraman (7) for CFS lipped channels, estimates the strength of LA compression members accurately.

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